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Abstract

This paper describes a research methodology that we believe has much to offer psychologists interested in a multimethod approach which is survey research. The survey as a method is one of the most common forms of research methods for collection of primary data from the field. It is a quantitative method and aims to gather data from many respondents to describe the frequency of an event and to generalise results from a smaller sample to larger population depending upon the nature and objectives of a study. Surveys are extensively used to collect and analyse varied types of data including psychological, social, political, economic, technical, cultural and educational among others. The paper also noted that although the social survey is a very old research technique, it is still one of the most favoured methods in social science study. The paper likewise reiterates the reason for psychologists employing to be understanding how people influence, and are influenced by their social environment and to the extent that psychological phenomena are universal across different types of people, it makes little difference precisely with whom psychological research is conducted even data collected from samples that are decidedly unrepresentative of the general population can be used to draw inferences about that population. The paper concluded that and recommended that despite its extensive use, the survey method is not always properly understood or carried out. While using this method, great attention needs to be given on selecting a representative sample, proper designing and pretesting of questionnaire to reduce error rates, administering, tabulating, and analysing the data.

Keywords: Survey Methods and Psychological Research

Introduction

Psychologists especially social psychologists have long recognized that every method of scientific inquiry is subject to limitations and that choosing among research methods inherently involves tradeoffs. With the control of a laboratory experiment, for example, comes an artificiality that raises questions about the generalizability of results. And yet the "naturalness" of a field study or an observational study can jeopardize the validity of causal inferences. The inevitability of such limitations has led many methodologists to advocate the use of multiple methods and to insist that substantive conclusions can be most confidently derived by triangulating across measures and methods that have nonoverlapping strengths and weaknesses (Brewer, 1986).

A variety of methodological approaches exist for individuals interested in conducting research. Selection of a research approach depends on a number of factors, including the purpose of the research, the type of research questions to be answered, and the availability of resources. The

The purpose of this paper is to describe survey research as one approach to the conduct of research so that the reader can critically evaluate the appropriateness of the conclusions from studies employing survey research. The survey remains one of the most commonly employed research techniques (Didier et al., 2010), especially in social sciences, social work, and other pertinent areas including health, population services, and census. This method was initiated by British social reformers in the Victorian era to obtain data on poverty and labouring class life (Ponto, 2015). Survey research is best used to gain information about large populations (Check & Schutt, 2012). Surveys do not control for or manipulate the independent variables or the treatments. It is also a nonexplanatory research design, as it uses a statistical test to measure variables and their relationship with others. Surveys could capture beliefs, practices, or situations from a random sample using a survey questionnaire or structured interview (Bhattacharjee, 2012).

The Survey as a method is one of the most common forms of research methods for collection of primary data from the field. It is a quantitative method and aims to gather data from many respondents to describe the frequency of an event and to generalise results from a smaller sample to larger population depending upon the nature and objectives of a study. Surveys are extensively used to collect and analyse varied types of data including psychological, social, political, economic, technical, cultural and educational among others. However, despite its extensive use, the survey method is not always properly understood or carried out. While using this method, great attention needs to be given on selecting a representative sample, proper designing and pretesting of questionnaire to reduce error rates, administering, tabulating, and analysing the data.

Objectives of the Paper

This paper describes a research methodology that has significant relevance in psychological research that involved larger sample.

Conceptual Definition of Terms

Survey: The literal meaning of the word 'survey' is to take or present a general view of something or examine something carefully. It involves investigation and examination and interviewing people (respondents) and asking them for information. Survey is conducted with a representative sample of the population being studied and it is assumed that information obtained from the sample is valid for the general population. As a quantitative method it describes, explains and predicts behaviours.

Survey research is a specific type of field study that involves the collection of data from a sample of elements (e.g., adult women) drawn from a well defined population (e.g., all adult women living in the United States) through the use of a questionnaire (Babbie, 1990).

Survey research is defined as "the collection of information from a sample of individuals through their responses to questions" (Check & Schutt, 2012). This type of research allows for a variety of methods to recruit participants, collect data, and utilize various methods of instrumentation. Survey research can use quantitative research strategies (e.g., using questionnaires with numerically rated items), qualitative research strategies (e.g., using open ended questions), or both strategies (i.e., mixed methods). As it is often used to describe and explore human behaviour, surveys are therefore frequently used in social and psychological research (Singleton & Straits, 2009). Information has

obtained from individuals and groups through the use of survey research for decades. It can range from asking a few targeted questions of individuals on a street corner to obtain information related to behaviours and preferences, to a more rigorous study using multiple valid and reliable instruments. Common examples of less rigorous surveys include marketing or political surveys of consumer patterns and public opinion polls.

Although the social survey is a very old research technique, it is still one of the most favoured methods in social science study. A probability survey is best used to describe a predetermined population using a small sample (Rubin & Babbie, 2016). Different researchers and methodology experts have defined social survey in different ways, which are discussed below: According to Duncan Mitchell's Dictionary of Sociology, a survey can be defined as "a systematic collection of facts about people living in a specific geographic, cultural or administrative area". Meanwhile, Bogardus described it as "the collection of data concerning the living and working conditions, broadly speaking of the people in a given community". Another definition offered by the Oxford Dictionary is that a survey undertakes a close examination of someone or something: It also includes evaluating and recording the area and characteristics of (a land) to build a map, plan, or description: It assesses the ideas, experience, or behaviour of (a group of people) by questioning them.

Creswell (2009) and Babbie (2012) indicated that survey research quantitatively describes trends, behaviours, or opinions of a population based on a sample study. Survey research can be divided into cross-sectional and longitudinal studies; both studies rely on questions or structured interviews to obtain sample data, which can be generalized to a population. Furthermore, Kendra (2016) stressed that 'a survey may attempt to obtain factual information or opinions of respondents'.

Survey research has historically included large population-based data collection. The primary purpose of this type of survey research was to obtain information describing characteristics of a large sample of individuals of interest relatively quickly. Large census surveys obtaining information reflecting demographic and personal characteristics and consumer feedback surveys are prime examples. These surveys were often provided through the mail and were intended to describe demographic characteristics of individuals or obtain opinions on which to base programs or products for a population or group. More recently, survey research has developed into a rigorous approach to research, with scientifically tested strategies detailing who to include (representative sample), what and how to distribute (survey method), and when to initiate the survey and follow up with nonresponders (reducing nonresponse error), in order to ensure a high-quality research process and outcome. Currently, the term "survey" can reflect a range of research aims, sampling and recruitment strategies, data collection instruments, and methods of survey administration.

Characteristics of Survey Method

Similar to other research methods, survey research has some distinguishing features, which set it apart from other social research methods. Different social science research methodology experts have characterized the survey method with various characteristics (Jackson, 2011). Check and

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Schmitt (2012) noted that, although the explanatory and measured variables in survey research are employed in the specification of the study scope, they cannot be explicitly controlled by the researcher. In this light, a social survey has three unique features, which are:

In the majority of cases, the survey method is used in quantitative research design and in examining the relations between variables.

(b) In survey research, the required particular data is collected from people.

(c) During the survey, some portion of the sample has been selected to generalize the total population.

Phillips et al. (2013) highlighted that an effective survey method must satisfy the following criteria: measurable survey objectives, good research designs; clear survey question; reasonable sampling plan when needed; effective survey response strategy; and purposeful data summary, display and reporting. Employing a good survey design is important to ensure the alignment between surveys and social sciences. A well designed survey should consider the demographic information of the targeted survey respondents (Ponto, 2015).

The focus of the survey needs to be very clear; for example, a researcher intending to survey the health situations of garments workers of Nigerian must have a specific view about the types of health problems he/she should focus on. The items in the questionnaire should be simple, clear, and free from jargon. It is good to avoid twopart questions, as some participants would only answer one part of the questions and leave the other part, and this could have some implications on the quality of the survey (Costanzo et'al., 2012). In a closeended questionnaire, it is useful to provide a section that allows comments from respondents. Questions should also be logically organized and presented in the questionnaire form and a logical sequence (Check & Schutt, 2012). The motivation of the respondent and openness of the researchers also contributes to the effectiveness of survey research (Farrell & Petersen, 2010).

Reasons for Psychologists to Conduct Survey Research

Social psychologists are interested in understanding how people influence, and are influenced by, their social environment. And to the extent that social psychological phenomena are universal across different types of people, it makes little difference precisely with whom social psychological research is conducted even data collected from samples that are decidedly unrepresentative of the general population can be used to draw inferences about that population. In recent years, however, psychologists have become increasingly sensitive to the impact of dispositional and contextual factors on human thought and social behaviour. Instead of broad statements about universal processes, social psychologists today are far more likely to offer qualified accounts of which people, under which conditions, are likely to exhibit a particular psychological phenomenon or process. And accordingly, social psychologists have increasingly turned their attention to interactions between various social psychological processes and characteristics of the individual, such as personality traits, identification with a social group or category, or membership in a distinct culture. In many cases, the nature of basic social

Psychological processes has been shown to depend to a large degree on characteristics of the individual.

The process by which attitude change occurs, for example, has been shown to differ for people who are low and high in what Petty and Cacioppo (1986) have termed "need for cognition," a general enjoyment of and preference for effortful thinking. Attitude change among people high in need for cognition tends to be mediated by careful scrutiny of the arguments in a persuasive appeal, whereas attitude change among people low in need for cognition tends to be based on cues in the persuasive message or context, such as the attractiveness of the source. Similarly, attributions have been shown to differ depending on social group membership (Hewstone, 1983). People tend to attribute positive behaviours by members of their own social group or category to stable, internal causes. Those same positive behaviours performed by a member of a different social group, however, are more likely to be attributed to transitory or external factors.

According to much recent research, culture may also moderate many social psychological phenomena. Markus and Kitayama (1991), for example, have argued that members of different cultures have different construals of the self and that these differences can have a profound impact on the nature of cognitive, emotional, and motivational process. These kinds of process-by-indifference interactions suggest that precisely who participates in social psychological research can have a profound impact on what results are obtained. And of course, for the vast majority of social psychological research, that "who" has been the infamous college sophomore. Sears (1986) has argued that the field's overwhelming reliance on this narrow base of research which may represent a serious problem for social psychology. Pointing to various attributes that are characteristic of young adults, Sears (1986) suggested that the "college sophomore" participants pool is unrepresentative of the general population in a number of important ways. Among other things, young adults are more susceptible to attitude change (Newcomb, 1991), exhibit less stable personality traits (Elder, 1989).

Doing so will require studies of samples that are representative of the general population, and inducing most members of such samples to visit a laboratory seems practically impossible. Studying a representative sample through field research, however, is relatively easy and surprisingly practical. Using the basic tenets of probability theory, survey researchers have developed a number of efficient strategies for drawing representative samples that are easy to contact. And when samples have been selected in such a manner, social psychologists can confidently generalize findings to the entire population. Furthermore, survey research provides ideal conditions for the exploration of Process x Individual Difference interactions because carefully selected samples reflect the full heterogeneity of the general population.

Empirical Review on Survey Methods

Fujimori et al. (2014) described the use of survey research in a study of the effect of communication skills training for oncologists on oncologist and patient outcomes (e.g., oncologist's performance and confidence and patient's distress, satisfaction, and trust). A sample of 30 oncologists from two hospitals was obtained and though the authors provided a power

analysis concluding an adequate number of oncologist participants to detect differences between baseline and followup scores, the conclusions of the study may not be generalizable to a broader population of oncologists. Oncologists were randomized to either an intervention group (i.e., communication skills training) or a control group (i.e., no training).

Fujimori et al. (2014) chose a quantitative approach to collect data from oncologist and patient participants regarding the study outcome variables. Selfreport numeric ratings were used to measure oncologist confidence and patient distress, satisfaction, and trust. Oncologist confidence was measured using two instruments each using 10point Likert rating scales. The Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS) was used to measure patient distress and has demonstrated validity and reliability in a number of populations including individuals with cancer (Bjelland et al., 2002). Patient satisfaction and trust were measured using 0 to 10 numeric rating scales. Numeric observer ratings were used to measure oncologist performance of communication skills based on a videotaped interaction with a standardized patient. Participants completed the same questionnaires at baseline and followup.

The authors clearly described what data were collected from all participants. Providing additional information about the manner in which questionnaires were distributed (i.e., electronic, mail), the setting in which data were collected (e.g., home, clinic), and the design of the survey instruments (e.g., visual appeal, format, content, arrangement of items) would assist the reader in drawing conclusions about the potential for measurement and nonresponse error. The authors described conducting a followup phone call or mail inquiry for non responders, using the Dillman et al. (2014) tailored design for survey research followup may have reduced nonresponse error.

According to Bertrand & Hughes (2005), surveys can be used for: collating descriptive information (television serial viewing habits of homemakers); making comparisons (comparing the soap opera viewing habits of teenage girls and teenage boys, or of teenage girls and housewives); and exploring relationships (for instance, exploring the relationship between soap opera viewing and level of formal education). A survey aims to seek diverse opinions and experiences into predetermined response categories and measures reactions of a large number of individuals to a limited set of questions. The method can be used to measure any aspect such as the number of people below the poverty line, the number of illiterates in a given place, people watching a particular television channel/programme, reading newspaper/listening to radio programme the list is endless. The numerical data thus obtained is expressed in frequency, percentages, averages, proportions etc. and presented in the form of tables, graphs and charts. Surveys thus involve numbers, magnitude, and measurement with the focus on objective and standardised means of inquiry. However, the method is not useful for indepth study of contexts and solutions to problems and it is often argued that ‘Surveys give a big picture of an issue under study but cannot capture the hidden nooks and crannies’.

According to Wiseman and Aron (1970), a survey is a “method for collecting and analysing social data via highly structured and often very detailed interviews and questionnaires in order to obtain information from large numbers of respondents presumed to be representative of a specific population.” The survey method can be applied for a variety of purposes. It can used to gather

business corporations use it to develop marketing strategies, political parties use it to develop campaign strategies; while government agencies use it to obtain data. The scope and depth of a survey may vary depending upon the nature of the study it may be broad or narrow, it may be limited to a small area or cover an entire state or even several states. Census, opinion polls and polls all use survey method for collecting data. In census all the members of a population group are covered thus eliminating the issues of representative sample. However, census requires a huge effort and at the national level can be undertaken only by the government that too only once in ten years in view of the expenses and challenges involved.

How to Use Surveys in Psychology

A survey can be used to investigate the characteristics, behaviours, or opinions of a group of people. These research tools can be used to ask questions about demographic information about characteristics such as sex, religion, ethnicity, and income.

They can also collect information on experiences, opinions, and even hypothetical scenarios. For example, researchers might present people with a possible scenario and then ask them how they might respond in that situation.

Types of Survey Methods

Surveys can be broadly classified as Descriptive surveys and Analytical or Explanatory surveys.

Descriptive Surveys: Descriptive research describes 'what is', and involves description, recording, analysis and interpretation of conditions that exist in a given area. Descriptive research uses both quantitative and qualitative research methods to study, describe and interpret what exists at present and provides useful and depth answers to research questions for decision makers and information users. It aims to examine a problematic situation, makes objective observations, analyse and interpret the data in clear and precise terms. Many a time, descriptive research itself is termed survey research. However, it is appropriate to consider survey as a descriptive research method. Descriptive surveys aim to describe or document the state of affairs as it exists at present the focus is on present day behaviour. The main characteristic of this type of survey is that the researcher has no control over the variables and s/he can report only of the happenings. Such surveys describe the population being studied and seek to relate this information to their opinions beliefs, values and behaviour etc. To take an example, audience research is conducted to obtain information about the demographic profile such as age, gender, area of residence, historical background, cultural factors, etc., while setting up a radio station. It is important to note that surveys are used to describe a situation at a given point in time; they cannot be used to describe either the past or the future.

Analytic Surveys: Analytical surveys attempt to describe and explain why certain situations exist, why people behave the way they do what causes certain type of behaviour. These are also called Explanatory surveys as they aim to determine cause and effects relationships between two or more variables. Researchers often use data from descriptive surveys to develop hypotheses and use analytic surveys to test their hypotheses. The results enable the researchers to examine the

relationships between variables and draw inferences. According to Wimmer & Dominick (2004) a survey has some well defined advantages, because it can be used to investigate problems in realistic settings where they happen rather than in laboratory or screening room under artificial conditions. The cost of conducting survey is relatively less as compared to other methods which can be further checked by using email and telephonic interviews.

Data Collection Tools in Survey

Survey research may use a variety of data collection methods with the most common being questionnaires and interviews.

Questionnaires: A questionnaire consists of a set of questions posed in a written form and in a definite order. The questionnaires are usually mailed to the respondents, either through regular post or email or administered in person for filling up the responses. The respondents are expected to go through the questionnaire, understand the questions and reply by writing in the relevant spaces and return the filled in questionnaires. Since the onus of replying remains on the receiver, it is important that the questionnaire is designed with great care to elicit responses. You will read more about designing of questionnaire in detail in subsection. While mailing the questionnaire through regular post, a self addressed stamped or prepaid cover is posted to increase the response rate. Questionnaires are useful for eliciting data on a variety of areas including demographic factors such as age, gender, family structure, class, education, occupation; media habits access to media, media exposure and utilisation patterns; likes and dislikes about specific programmes, characters, issues projected in media such as violence, crime and so on.

Questionnaires may be self administered or administered by a professional, may be administered individually or in a group, and typically include a series of items reflecting the research aims. Questionnaires may include demographic questions in addition to valid and reliable research instruments (Costanzo et al., 2012; DuBenske et al., 2014). It is helpful to the reader when authors describe the contents of the survey questionnaire so that the reader can interpret and evaluate the potential for errors of validity (e.g., items or instruments that do not measure what they are intended to measure) and reliability (e.g., items or instruments that do not measure a construct consistently). Helpful examples of articles that describe the survey instruments exist in the literature (Buerhaus et'al., 2012). Questionnaires may be in paper form and mailed to participants, delivered in an electronic format via email or an Internet based program such as Survey Monkey, or a combination of both, giving the participant the option to choose which method is preferred (Ponto et'al., 2010). Using a combination of methods of survey administration can help to ensure better sample coverage (i.e., all individuals in the population having a chance of inclusion in the sample) therefore reducing coverage error (Dillman et'al., 2014; Singleton & Straits, 2009). For example, if a researcher were to only use an Internet delivered questionnaire, individuals without access to a computer would be excluded from participation. Self administered mailed, group, or Internet based questionnaires are relatively low cost and practical for a large sample (Check & Schutt, 2012).

Strengths

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A questionnaire is a convenient and economical tool for collecting large amounts of data from small as well as large population groups. It is an impersonal way to obtain data and ensures a certain degree of anonymity to the respondents; it can be used to obtain personal and to some extent, sensitive information and minimise bias during data collection. It places less pressure on respondents for immediate response who can respond to the questionnaire at his/her own pace and time.

Limitations

A questionnaire, however, is also beset with a number of limitations the most important being that it does not produce a high rate of recovery. Studies have revealed that the response rate of questionnaire is rarely more than 1215 percent and in some cases even less and in such cases, the data has limited validity. Further, a questionnaire can be administered only to those who can read and write reasonably well and cannot be used with small children and illiterates. If a respondent misinterprets a question, there could be inconsistencies in replies. Moreover, respondent may give hurried responses lacking depth resulting in superficiality in responses. They may not reply to all questions and leave some blanks resulting in incomplete data. Once the information has been collected and compiled, analysis of data can be time consuming. Moreover, obtaining representative samples may be difficult leading to sampling errors. All these limitations emphasise the need for taking due care while using this tool of data collection.

Interviews Schedules: Some of the limitations of the questionnaire method can be overcome through Interview schedules or personal schedules. Interview, as you know, is a conversation between the researcher and the respondent it involves asking questions, listening to individuals and recording their responses. It is generally conducted through face-to-face interaction though it can also be conducted by telephone, emails and other means. A schedule, when sent through post, email etc. is known as questionnaire but when administered in face-to-face situation is called interview schedule or personal schedule as it is a personalised way of data collection. The interview schedule is prepared well in advance before proceeding for data collection. The questions are carefully worded and delivered identically to all respondents and the resulting data are quantitative and comparable.

Conducting interviews is another approach to data collection used in survey research. Interviews may be conducted by phone, computer, or in person and have the benefit of visually identifying the nonverbal response(s) of the interviewee and subsequently being able to clarify the intended question. An interviewer can use probing comments to obtain more information about a question or topic and can request clarification of an unclear response (Singleton & Straits, 2009). Interviews can be costly and time intensive, and therefore are relatively impractical for large samples.

Some authors advocate for using mixed methods for survey research when no one method is adequate to address the planned research aims, to reduce the potential for measurement and nonresponse error, and to better tailor the study methods to the intended sample (Dillman et al., 2014; Singleton & Straits, 2009). For example, a mixed methods survey research approach may begin with distributing a questionnaire and following up with telephone interviews to clarify

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ear survey responses (Singleton & Straits, 2009). Mixed methods might also be used when visual or auditory deficits preclude an individual from completing a questionnaire or participating in an interview.

Strengths

An interview schedule is useful in collecting data from rural and illiterate/semi literate respondents who cannot use questionnaires. Since the interviewer is in a face-to-face situation with the respondents, s/he can build rapport with the respondents, spend time with them and can explain the questions, if needed. The response rate of interview schedule is high as the researcher is in direct contact with the respondents. It is an effective tool for obtaining information about prevalence and distribution of an issue from large number of people. The schedule once designed can be shown and discussed in advance to weed out inconsistencies or jumps etc. It can be completed quickly in the field and is economical on time. The data obtained is comparable hence easier to analyse. While less skill is required on the part of the interviewer when collecting data for his/her own research; the field investigators need to be oriented and trained before administering the interview schedule in larger projects involving a number of field investigators for data collection. Field investigators need to understand the broad aim and objectives of the research study and the importance of questions to record complete responses in a proper way. They may need to be trained in how questions should be asked; whether questions can be rephrased; or follow up questions can be asked. They also need to be trained on how to approach a respondent, build rapport, and what to do if the respondent refuses to answer any or all questions.

Limitations

Interview schedules are also beset with some limitations. Much skill is required to create an interview schedule as highly structured questionnaires yield little insight into how people feel about the issues involved. At times, an interviewer may not be able to respond to a valuable issue/situation which emerges during an interview but does not appear on the schedule. Since the researcher is expected to go to the field and meet the respondents to record their replies, it can be time consuming and expensive. It may be difficult to find those selected in the sample, and even if available, respondents may be reluctant to answer some questions. There could be cultural, linguistic and other forms of barriers. Their travel expenses, lodging boarding charges also need to be taken into account. In a larger study, individual differences among field investigators may affect the quality of data hence orientation of the researchers is a must. The tendency to get too personally involved with the respondents at times may turn intrusive and lead to the risk of introducing bias in the results. Care needs to be taken that the researcher does not impose his/her own perspective on an issue. Some of these limitations can be overcome through training of the researchers.

Sampling Method in Survey Research

The goal of sampling strategies in survey research is to obtain a sufficient sample that is representative of the population of interest. It is often not feasible to collect data from an entire population of interest (e.g., all individuals with lung cancer); therefore, a subset of the population

A sample is used to estimate the population responses (e.g., individuals with lung cancer currently receiving treatment). A large random sample increases the likelihood that the responses from the sample will accurately reflect the entire population. In order to accurately draw conclusions about the population, the sample must include individuals with characteristics similar to the population.

It is therefore necessary to correctly identify the population of interest (e.g., individuals with lung cancer currently receiving treatment vs. all individuals with lung cancer). The sample will ideally include individuals who reflect the intended population in terms of all characteristics of the population (e.g., sex, socioeconomic characteristics, symptom experience) and contain a similar distribution of individuals with those characteristics. Fujimori et al. (2014), for example, were interested in the population of oncologists. The authors obtained a sample of oncologists from two hospitals in Japan. These participants may or may not have similar characteristics to all oncologists in Japan.

Participants recruitment strategies can affect the adequacy and representativeness of the sample obtained. Using diverse recruitment strategies can help improve the size of the sample and help ensure adequate coverage of the intended population. For example, if a survey researcher intends to obtain a sample of individuals with breast cancer representative of all individuals with breast cancer in the United States, the researcher would want to use recruitment strategies that would recruit both women and men, individuals from rural and urban settings, individuals receiving and not receiving active treatment, and so on. Because of the difficulty in obtaining samples representative of a large population, researchers may focus the population of interest to a subset of individuals (e.g., women with stage III or IV breast cancer). Large census surveys require extremely large samples to adequately represent the characteristics of the population because they are intended to represent the entire population.

Relevance of Surveys Methods in Psychology

Surveys in psychology are vital because they allow researchers to:

- Understand the experiences, opinions, and behaviors of the participants
- Evaluate respondent attitudes and beliefs
- Look at the risk factors in a sample
- Assess individual differences
- Evaluate the success of interventions or preventative programs

Advantages of Survey Methods in Psychology

Survey method has the following advantages in comparison with other methods:

(i) **Direct & close contact between Researcher and the Respondents**

- In this method the researcher has to come in close and direct contact of the people, whom he wants to study.
- A survey brings the researcher in a position to come face to face with the realities of life and see things personally.

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(ii)

Greater Objectivity
The survey method avoids the possibility of personal biases.

Large number of field workers is employed for the collection of data.

Thus, the data are not influenced by any one man's view or belief. Hence, greater degree of objectivity may be obtained under this method.

(iii) **Testing the Validity of Theories**

- Survey method is very useful in testing the validity of many theories.
- In many cases, it has been observed that actual surveys have led to entirely different results than arrived at through purely theoretical interpretations.

(iv) **Formulation and Testing of Hypothesis**

- Surveys have proved this usefulness in leading to the formulation of hypothesis.
- At a more advance stage, surveys are also helpful in putting the hypothesis to test.
- A general survey brings light to a number of problems that would have not been possible by pure theoretical analysis. The survey results may also provide new hypothesis that may be completely outside the scope of the existing theory and may lead to the new theory.

(v) **Social Surveys are based on actual observations**

- Under social survey methods, a researcher is in a position to observe the activities of a group under study from a much closer distance.
- It helps a researcher to have a better insight to their doing.
- Personal approach enables the researcher in getting reliable information as the investigator is in a position to clear up doubts and misunderstandings on the spot specially when the respondents are literates.

(vi) **Universal Application**

- It is one of widely used methods.
- In case of social sciences, where experimental method is not easily possible, survey method is the most scientific method for providing reliable information and thereby drawing inferences.

Others are:

- Efficient
- Less expensive
- Easy to create and administer
- Diverse uses

Disadvantages of Survey Methods in Psychology

Although survey method has a great significance, there are some limitations commonly attributed to this method: Experts suggested that return rates of 85% or higher are considered excellent, but anything below 60% might severely impact the sample's representativeness.

- **Problems with construction and administration:** Poor survey construction and administration can undermine otherwise well designed studies.

Inaccuracy: The answer choices provided in a survey may not be an accurate reflection of how the participants actually feel.

Poor response rates: While random sampling is generally used to select participants, response rates can bias the results of a survey. Strategies to improve response rates sometimes include offering financial incentives, sending personalized invitations, and reminding participants to complete the survey.

- **Biased results:** The social desirability bias can lead people to respond in a way that makes them look better than they really are. For example, a respondent might report that they engage in more healthy behaviors than they do in real life.
- Survey method is costly, time consuming and wasteful in certain cases where the objectives are limited.
- The survey method is unsuitable if the number of persons to be surveyed is very large or they are spread over a large geographical area.
- The survey method lacks flexibility. In case of inadequate or incomplete research design or any change in research design, may mean conducting the survey afresh as there is no other remedy in such cases.
- Under this method it is very difficult to verify the accuracy of the data collected because accuracy of the data, to a great extent, is dependent upon the honesty, sincerity, personal qualities and un biased attitude of the enumerators and cooperation of the respondents.

Others are

- May be poorly designed
- Limited answer choices can influence results
- Subject to social desirability bias

Conclusion

Psychological surveys can be powerful, convenient, and informative research tools. Researchers often utilize surveys in psychology to collect data about how participants think, feel, or behave. While useful, it is important to construct these surveys carefully to avoid asking leading questions and reduce bias. Survey research is a useful and legitimate approach to research that has clear benefits in helping to describe and explore variables and constructs of interest. Survey research, like all research, has the potential for a variety of sources of error, but several strategies exist to reduce the potential for error.

The survey method is a way to collect information about a lot of people, which can help us learn more about what they think and feel. The survey method is a research method that is used to collect data that is not as detailed as data that is collected using other methods. This makes the survey method easier to understand and use, which is why it is often used in quantitative research. Relational research is a type of research where scientists study relationships between different things. For example, they might study how people interact with each other, or how different groups of people interact. Survey research is a type of research where scientists ask a lot of people a lot of questions. In the survey method, researchers collect information about a specific group of people. This is different from correlational research, which investigates the relationship between two or more variables.

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Survey research is good at collecting data that is broadly representative of the population, but it can't always determine why things happen or provide detailed information.

Recommendations

At the end of the paper the following recommendations were made:

- i. The social survey remains one of the most effective and popular methods of investigation in the social sciences because it allows huge data collection.
- ii. Psychologists and other social science researchers are recommended to use survey method because carefully monitoring data collection permits early detection of problems and seems likely to improve data quality.
- iii. It also help in self administered questionnaire and researchers monitor incoming data for signs that respondents may have trouble with the questionnaire so as to be guided.

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